

Synthesis of Polynitroaryl Derivatives of 3-Aryl-1*H*,4*H*-dihydro-4,6,6-trimethyl-pyrimidine-2-thiols as Possible Fungicides

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Manuscript received 30 July 1983, revised 6 March 1985, accepted 7 June 1986

Fortyeight new 3-aryl-1,4-dihydro-2-polynitroarylmercapto-4,6,6-trimethylpyrimidines (1-6) have been prepared in good yields by the condensation of appropriate active chlorobenzene and pyrimidine-2-thiol (A) in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in absolute ethanol. Mass spectra of three compounds (1b, 1e and 1g) have revealed that in addition to NO_2 and Me radical's loss from the molecular ion, the predominant fragment ions appear at respective m/z values which correspond to the molecular ions of pyrimidine thiols Ab, Ae and Ag, respectively. The further fragmentation pattern has been studied and it has been observed that loss of Me gives base peak in each case.

PYRIMIDINE nucleus has been employed as a basis for the synthesis of chemotherapeutic agents and a large number of its derivatives have been reported to possess various biological properties, such as antitumor¹, antimalarial², diuretic³, anti-inflammatory⁴, antithyroid⁵ and antifungal⁶.

The thiol group attached to a heterocyclic nucleus may enhance fungitoxicity⁷. The sulphides have been reported to be more biologically active than the parent mercapto⁸ compounds. These observations coupled with the fact that polynitroaryl sulphides possess strong fungicidal activity, prompted us to undertake the synthesis of polynitroaryl derivatives of 3-aryl-1,4-dihydro-4,6,6-trimethyl-pyrimidine-2-thiols. Thus, we report in the present paper, the synthesis of fortyeight title compounds (1-6) which were obtained in good yields by the condensation of appropriate active chlorobenzenes (polynitrochlorobenzenes) and pyrimidine thiols (A) in the presence of excess of anhydrous sodium acetate and absolute alcohol.

Structures of the final compounds were confirmed by their melting points, elemental analysis, ir spectral data and mass spectral fragmentation of a few compounds. In the ir spectra of 1, absorption band due to SH ($\sim 2600\text{ cm}^{-1}$) disappeared and in addition these compounds showed sharp and strong absorption peaks due to NO_2 groups appearing at $1570\text{-}80$ and $1350\text{-}60\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Mass spectra of three compounds 1b, 1e and 1g were also recorded in order to give further support to the structures and to study their fragmentation pattern. The molecular ions do not appear as base peak in all the three cases. Base peaks are observed at respective m/z values obtained by the loss of Me

1a-6a, Ar = C_6H_5 ; 1b-6b, Ar = $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-CH}_3$; 1c-6c, Ar = $\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{-OH}$; 1d-6d, Ar = $m\text{-CH}_3\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4$; 1e-6e, Ar = $p\text{-OH-C}_6\text{H}_4$; 1f-6f, Ar = $m\text{-Cl-C}_6\text{H}_4$; 1g-6g, Ar = $p\text{-Cl-C}_6\text{H}_4$; 1h-6h, Ar = 2,3-dichlorophenyl.

Reagents. (i) Anhydrous CH_3COONa , absolute ethanol.

Scheme 1

radical from the molecular ions of the corresponding pyrimidine thiols (Ae) which are the predominant peaks and undergo a variety of fragmentations. The other important losses from molecular ion were due to Me and NO_2 radicals.

* 184 Abu Lane, Meerut-250 001.

All these processes have been shown in Chart 1 by taking the example of 1e. 3-p-tolyl-1,4-dihydro-4,6,6-trimethylpyrimidine-2-thiol (Ae) and then this ion suffers a loss of Me

Chart 1

here that the predominant peak 246 due to the molecular ion of 3-p-tolyl-1,4-dihydro-4,6,6-trimethylpyrimidine-2-thiol radical to give the base peak at m/z 231. This ion also undergoes a loss of S to give an ion of poor

intensity (5%) at m/z 214. The ion at m/z 214 reveals a loss of C_3H_6 to yield an intense ion at m/z 172 which can be explained due to the formation of 2-methyl-1-*p*-tolylimidazole, a stable compound. The ion due to imidazole derivative can undergo variety of fragmentation as shown in Chart 1. As after getting molecular ion due to thiol (Ae, m/z 246) all the further fragments are explained from this molecule. Mass spectrum of Ae was separately recorded and all peaks were found to be identical with those observed in the mass spectrum of 1e.

The mass spectral data of three compounds (1b, 1e, 1g) have been listed in Table 1.

It is interesting to mention here that peaks appearing at m/z 91 in 1b and 1e, the two isomeric compounds, differ in their relative abundance. 1b and 1e show relative intensity as 100 and 25%, respectively, thereby indicating that the former corresponds to tropylium cation (which is obtained from benzyl cation and is more stable) and the latter to *p*-tolyl cation (lesser stable). Thus, the two isomeric compounds may be distinguished by this study.

TABLE 1—MASS SPECTRAL DATA OF 1b, 1e AND 1g (ARRANGED TO DISPLAY THE COINCIDENCE OF FRAGMENT IONS IN COMPOUNDS)

	m/z (% intensity)		
1b	1e	1g	
412(34)	412(30)	432/434(42)*	
397(8)	397(8)	417/419(10)	
366(10)	366(11)	386/388(13)	
246(95)	246(31)	266/268(45)	
231(100)	231(100)	251/253(100)	
214(4)	214(5)	—	
172(26)	172(25)	192/194(22)	
132(15)	132(12)	152/154(15)	
106(5)	106(6)	126/128(4)	
105(8)	105(5)	125/127(4)	
91(100)	91(25)	111/113(20)	
81(8)	81(10)	101/103(5)	

* Typical chlorine isotopic profile loss of chlorine radical from m/z 192/194.

TABLE 2

Compd. no.	M.p.* °C	Yield %	Formula**
1a	159-61	80	$C_{10}H_{16}N_4O_4S$
1b	163	85	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4S$
1c	167	90	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4S$
1d	157	82	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4S$
1e	169-71	70	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4S$
1f	155	74	$C_{10}H_{17}N_4O_4ClS$
1g	170	84	$C_{10}H_{17}N_4O_4ClS$
1h	205	69	$C_{10}H_{16}N_4O_4Cl_2S$
2a	107	75	$C_{10}H_{17}N_4O_4ClS$
2b	115	80	$C_{20}H_{16}N_4O_4ClS$
2c	126	86	$C_{20}H_{16}N_4O_4ClS$
2d	101	78	$C_{20}H_{16}N_4O_4ClS$
2e	110	66	$C_{20}H_{16}N_4O_4ClS$
2f	98	65	$C_{10}H_{16}N_4O_4Cl_2S$
2g	119	82	$C_{10}H_{16}N_4O_4Cl_2S$
2h	147	60	$C_{10}H_{16}N_4O_4Cl_2S$
3a	104	85	$C_{10}H_{17}N_4O_4ClS$
3b	112	88	$C_{20}H_{16}N_4O_4ClS$
3c	118	90	$C_{20}H_{16}N_4O_4ClS$

(Table 2 contd.)

3d	104-5	92	$C_{20}H_{16}N_4O_4ClS$
3e	114-5	80	$C_{20}H_{16}N_4O_4ClS$
3f	95	75	$C_{10}H_{16}N_4O_4Cl_2S$
3g	120	73	$C_{10}H_{16}N_4O_4Cl_2S$
3h	151	68	$C_{10}H_{16}N_4O_4Cl_2S$
4a	181	88	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4S$
4b	174	75	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4S$
4c	135	82	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4S$
4d	127	80	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4S$
4e	156	78	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4S$
4f	196	81	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4ClS$
4g	202	80	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4ClS$
4h	225	60	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4Cl_2S$
5a	209	90	$C_{20}H_{16}N_4O_4S$
5b	215	80	$C_{20}H_{16}N_4O_4S$
5c	185	85	$C_{20}H_{16}N_4O_4S$
5d	198	88	$C_{20}H_{16}N_4O_4S$
5e	226	82	$C_{20}H_{16}N_4O_4S$
5f	231	75	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4ClS$
5g	217	79	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4ClS$
5h	269	69	$C_{20}H_{16}N_4O_4Cl_2S$
6a	149	79	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4S$
6b	155	68	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4S$
6c	162	85	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4S$
6d	160	81	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4S$
6e	157	60	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4S$
6f	149	70	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4ClS$
6g	165	78	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4ClS$
6h	187	74	$C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_4Cl_2S$

* Solvents used for crystallisation; aqueous EtOH for 1b, 2b, 2c. C_6H_6 for 2d, 2h, 3a, 3h, 5b, 5h. EtOH for the rest of the compounds. ** Satisfactory N and S analysis obtained for all the compounds.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries in H_2SO_4 bath and are uncorrected. Ir (KBr) spectra were recorded on a Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer. Mass spectra were scanned on Hitachi RUM-60, MS-12 and Varian MAT-731 spectrometers.

Polynitrohalogenobenzenes: The following reactive halogeno compounds were used for condensation with pyrimidine-2-thiols: 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene, 1,3-dichloro-4,6-dinitrobenzene, 1,4-dichloro-2,6-dinitrobenzene, 1-chloro-5-methyl-2,4-dinitrobenzene, 1-chloro-5-methyl-2,4,6-trinitrobenzene, and 1-chloro-2-methyl-4,6-dinitrobenzene. All of the compounds were prepared by methods reported earlier⁹⁻¹³.

Substituted-pyrimidine-2-thiols: 3-Aryl-4,6,6-trimethyl-1,4-dihydro-pyrimidine-2-thiols (A) were prepared according to the reported method¹⁴. A brief procedure for the synthesis of Ae is described. A mixture of mesityl oxide (49 g, 0.5 M), ammonium thiocyanate, (38 g, 0.5 M), *p*-toluidine (53.5 g, 0.5 M) and water (100 ml) was agitated in a reaction flask. HCl (55 g) was added in 10 min at 20°. The buff coloured crystalline product precipitated when heated to reflux. The precipitate was washed with water and crystallised twice from ethanol (104.6 g), m.p. 191° (lit. 191°); M^+ , m/z 246 (calculated mol. wt. 246), major peaks m/z 246 (30%), 231 (100%), 215 (5%); 214 (5%), 172 (26%), 132 (12%), 106 (6%), 105 (5%), 91 (27%), 81 (9%) and 77 (12%). The

mass spectral fragmentation of Ae confirms its structure.

3-Aryl-1, 4-dihydro-2-(polynitroaryl)mercapto-4,6,6-trimethylpyrimidines (1-6) · General procedure : Pyrimidine-2-thiol (A ; 0.005 M) was dissolved in minimum volume of boiling absolute ethanol. Anhydrous sodium acetate was added in excess and boiling was continued for about 30 min. To the boiling mixture, an ethanolic solution (0.005 M) of polynitrochlorobenzene (I-VI) was added in portions. The contents were refluxed for 5-6 h (refluxing time for the completion of the reaction was monitored by tlc). The contents of the reaction flask were then poured into cold water and kept overnight. The grey to brown coloured solid material so obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallised. All the characterisation data of the compounds are given in Table 2.

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance to one of the authors (A.K.) is gratefully acknowledged under the F.A.T. programme from U.G.C., New Delhi.

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